

>>On the topic of the Data leylines, and in pursuit of the Data Aether (Dæther)

In this letter:

- Update on MIMS 2.5.1 - is there a Standing Wave in business profits?
- Analysis of Bitcoin Futures (BTF) using Thinkorswim studies and fundamental analysis techniques (particularly fibonacci sequences)
- In search of the Dæther: a proposal for the gaseous or *plasma* modeling of the data sciences and the *Power of Numbers*, as well as a short primer re-discussion of MIMS 1.2 (now 2.101)
- Six hypotheses for the dæther model testing. (2.102.1-6)

MIMS 2.102 - In pursuit of the Data Aether (*Dæther*)

January 2022

Best Viewed at: <https://bit.ly/31rtAlr>

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM
Lexington, KY

MIMS 2.5.1 - An Update on the “Financial Velocity”; is it a Standing Wave?	3
MIMS 2.101 - Data Leylines, an Update	4
A hypothesis? A mere side thought?	4
MIMS 2.1.212 - Analysis of Bitcoin Futures as a Futurization	5
EPEMC :: Modeling the Dæther as a Gaseous Plasma, proposition	13
Inflation, more than aptly named?	13
Money Velocity: a sign of Dæthereal Mechanics?	14
Proposal	15

Re: What is the proposed Dæther?

From the Desk of Sf. Ramon Careaga, founder EPEMC, www.epemcgateway.com

Dear Readers,

As I previously had mentioned, there may in fact be data “ley lines” which connect portions of the *Power of Numbers*¹ together, linking thusly information, data, maths, and numerology, as well as other wells of numeric aether. If there are such ley lines, we should be able to experience or see these, and because of the “Big G”² structure, actually we would not be capable of removing the mind from the issue. However, we can compare what are essentially different wells but contained within a similar MIMS, such as finance, and look for connections which strain credulity as far as coincidence as a hypothesis goes.

In pursuit of this we have new evidence, and we have found unique behaviors in business data. I am able to vouch for these because I am the purveyor of all this data. As for my defense against cries of “blinding!” or “bias!” I would say simply that a business has to perform, and so most of my time is spent keeping it alive, not trying to find ways to control the variable (when customers come in and buy). As for crypto I have very little overall control, after all. As for the drawings and studies on the BTF, while I have control, I’ve provided evidence that I made predictions **ahead** of the demonstrations of the behaviors. Now it may be that the “market maker” in Bitcoin Futures is a person doing this analysis, and that cannot be ruled out. But I doubt it. I tend to think it’s all automated and algorithmic. Even if it weren’t, from my subjective experience, I am still mimsing as in trying to predict future events. The mimsical studies, such as bollinger bands, are all mathematical algorithms and therefore also controlled in the *N* power, and we should expect some type of connection, be it from data ley lines or not.

Finally, I wish to propose a thought and literal experiment about the “data aether” or Daether - as I am coining it - which may provide a unification of PEMC, EPEMC, MIMS, and the various *P* and *N* power attributes that are in control of the Universe.

Figure 1 - “the Big G” (enhanced with fibonacci); credit: author³

¹ https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions

²

https://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0

³ https://www.academia.edu/53713967/MIMS_1_12_Self_Consistency_of_the_Big_G_Diagram

MIMS 2.5.1 - An Update on the “Financial Velocity”; is it a Standing Wave?

Figure 1 - Profit⁴ (10%, by week); appearance of standing waves with a peak frequency of 22 weeks?; credit: author/"financial velocity"⁵; note the asymmetry of the peaks and valleys

Standing Waves are produced by some forms of repeated phenomenon. Also, J. Davey noted that the above shows some sawtooth waveform, which may suggest some form of capacitance, which combined with my business power equation in MIMS 2.0, we may be looking at an RLC model (or the ability to create *some* form of analog circuit design of a business), which coil then be tuned by business executives for the improvement of operations. This would fall under the category of Operations Research, etc.

Figure 2 - Standing Waves; credit: Wiki

All that can be done from here out is to keep track through 2022 and observe if the pulsing of the wave continues. As for the periodicity, it isn't overtly clear to me why the period is 22 weeks and not quarterly.

⁴ Using the www.bluelotushealth.com clinic as a MIMS for a mimsical discussion, mapped by the MIMS spreadsheet! "All mimsy were the borogroves..."

⁵ Note: ignore the PPP injection on the far left, which is not organic profits.

MIMS 2.101 - Data Leylines, an Update

Previously I also brought in a graph that was showing potential interaction of two different aether tranches - personal crypto and business savings - as occurred on or around September 12th, 2021.

Figure 3 - "Financial Velocity"; credit: author; note that the leftmost arrow was in paper 1 on the issue

I am here to note two more interesting correlations. The first is a series of 2 arrows which could easily be described as "coincidental" *if* it weren't for the

fact that in late September, early October there wasn't a unique event: I fell in love.

Secondly, note the inflation of the two in late October and again in December, which happened to correlate also with the facts of (a) personal tragedy mixed with holiday pain and (b) holiday boom (see the BTF graphs of beforehand). Note the inflation is between unrelated (directly, only through me, and there were no new investments at this time) tranches of data, which bolsters the data leyline hypothesis.

A hypothesis? A mere side thought?

Could data leylines be a "counter-rotating vortex" pair⁶, a Dæther Birkeland Current⁷ (DBC)? It does appear that counter-rotation of currents keep repeating, and it seems likely to be related to the issue of R. Distinti's "Vortrix Algebra"⁸ explanation of the "imaginary number" as being merely a 90 degree rotation, which may explain the magnetic-electrical connection and in particular EMF radiation behavior in terms of polarity.⁹

⁶

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/314258249_Standing_waves_in_a_counter-rotating_vortex_filament_pair

⁷ <https://deepblue.lib.umich.edu/bitstream/handle/2027.42/145256/rog20162.pdf?sequence=1>

⁸ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TSPsi3c_nh8&list=PL2fbwSsQ2zIVFTOb1FOPnqNMLsuWgFXHb

⁹ See

https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top_Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Aether_Field_Theories_including_EPEMC pp. 60

MIMS 2.1.212¹⁰ - Analysis of Bitcoin Futures as a Futurization^{11 12}

Chart for BTF 180 D 4h printed on 12/28/21, 3:51 PM

Figure 4 - Analysis from 12/28/21 which showed the price of BTF drop from the channel of bullish gains back towards the final fibonacci fan; credit: Thinkorswim/author (all)

¹⁰ 2.1 = Finance; 2 for cryptocurrency, 1 for Bitcoin, 2 for Futures; Cryptomining as a MIMS was 2.1.1

¹¹ MIMS 1.0

https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPEMC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EPEMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability

¹² and fundamental use of 2.101

EPEMC :: Data Science :: Crypto :: Finance
Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

The reader can be forgiven for not understanding how this is significant. Let me explain. On the 17th of December I actually started the present analysis, and I have proof of this:

Figure 5 - My warning to a confidant about buying Bitcoin early. It had to do with the price nearing the first fibonacci fan, and downward pressure.

Figure 6 - a Closeup (sorry for angle, this is a photo of my monitor)

Chart for BTF 180 D 4h printed on 12/28/21, 2:37 PM

Figure 7 - The Bollinger Analysis on the 28th. One can see that after the downward pressure on the 19th, from 20th to 27th there was a decent little run on BTF, but it got a lot of people buying in BTC at 50k and it then crashed, showing the pressure of the fibonacci fans.

Without a data leyline connection, I am strained to see how any of these things can be proven together!

Chart for BTF 180 D 4h printed on 1/4/22, 9:34 AM

Figure 8 - a “3 green arrow” analysis showing the MACD histograms and stochastics of the past, as well as the fibonacci time series and the fibonacci spirals¹³.

¹³ Remember how important fibonacci is in our Big G and EPEMC in general!

Chart for BTF 180 D 4h printed on 1/4/22, 9:29 AM

Figure 9 - Closeup of the previously made (on 28th) channel analysis; note the prediction of the lower channel bar to create the bounce on the 2nd of January 2022

The most important thing to notice, however, is the effect of the fibonacci spiral as the fan crosses, to create the upwards bounce. This effect is well known with stock, options, and futures traders, and that's how I learned about it.

EPEMC :: Data Science :: Crypto :: Finance
Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

Chart for BTF 180 D 4h printed on 1/4/22, 9:35 AM

Figure 10 - A better view of the entire spiral, and how the Changes are happening. Please note how the last fibonacci fan provides pressure upon the BTF price... up until the burst upwards at the spiral.

Chart for BTF 180 D 4h printed on 1/4/22, 9:36 AM

Figure 11 - Same view but the Moving Average Ribbon; please note the strong likelihood of the price to continue into a sideways channel; a price bounce was predicted, and tomorrow 1/5/21 is a scheduled volume burst.

Chart for BTF 180 D 4h printed on 1/4/22, 9:37 AM

Figure 12 - Bollinger Band agreement with my opinion. Bear in mind the drawings added are mine, the study is algorithmic

EPEMC :: Modeling the Dæther as a Gaseous Plasma, proposition

Presuppose that numbers (I) do not exist on a timeline, or axis, but instead exist in a n th-hyperdimensional volumetric geometry “force-free” aligned field, simulated in this case (in our minds) as a 3-dimensional gas.

What would the P power principles which govern things like $PV=nRT$ really look like in a dæther context? In my mind’s eye, I see neutrino sized particles moving quite apart, exerting charge like fields upon one another. In reality, I do not imagine or think that numbers are particles, but rather particles are numbers substantiated. To some degree, subatomic particles “mass” is just electronvolt ranges, seemingly arbitrary, and there may exist alternate dimensions wherein their values are completely different.

Let us consider - as a mental thought experiment - the effects of:

- ❖ Inflation
- ❖ Money Velocity

We will also then inquire (internally, as well as to a data scientist) about the importance of it being a crypto market versus other financial markets, etc.

Inflation, more than aptly named?

The financial definition of inflation¹⁴ is: *“Inflation¹⁵ is the decline of purchasing power of a given currency over time. A quantitative estimate of the rate at which the decline in purchasing power occurs can be reflected in the increase of an average price level of a basket of selected goods and services in an economy over some period of time. The rise in the general level of prices, often expressed as a percentage, means that a unit of currency effectively buys less than it did in prior periods.”*¹⁶

Famously, this is caused by the “printing” of money¹⁷ aka increasing the money supply. Basically, consider the term analogous to filling up a balloon or beach ball, with air.

Figure 13 - Inflating ball ([gif](#)); credit: giphy

Obviously there are three things that interest us right away

1. Surface tension and thinning of the “membrane”
2. Potential for “bursting the bubble”
3. Increasing explosiveness (risk) with inflation

¹⁴ “The most commonly used inflation indexes are the Consumer Price Index (CPI) and the Wholesale Price Index (WPI).”

¹⁵ “Inflation is sometimes classified into three types: Demand-Pull inflation, Cost-Push inflation, and Built-In inflation.”

¹⁶ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/i/inflation.asp>

¹⁷ Eg. Quantitative Easing

As we consider this issue, how much of life - in our limited time and experience - is full of situations where pressure is applied, often without our awareness of how or where this pressure comes from? When we feel these peer and other pressures, we typically find explanations which are accurate in terms of their sources, but imprecise in terms of the mechanism by which the pressure is applied.

Why is this? (II) We don't see these forces, and perhaps we don't see something more or less tangible: the dæther.

Nevertheless, when we consider the "ball" of economics here, we are very much concerned with the application of forces, particularly puncturing forces, which could disturb the surface tension and release the container of tension, causing explosion and rapid deflation.

Consider this, too, that the deflation is not necessarily in the numbers associated with that which inflated. Take the classic case of "hyperinflation": first the currency inflates, and the country benefits. Then it hyperinflates, and the currency collapses. Then the economy collapses, causing deflation, but in the meantime the collapse spreads - virally as it were - into sector by sector collapse, until the total numeric output and all sorts of numeric measures of the entire country, in areas beyond economics, all collapse. It is as if toxic particles are set free, and they explode outwards, landing within other objects. Are they governed by aetheric birkeland currents and magnetic tunnels? Is there anything at all to the DBC concept? Or is it perhaps accomplished via another, again hidden, interface?

Money Velocity: a sign of Dæthereal Mechanics?

In the second consideration, again economic, we consider the behavior of money in terms of Newtonian mechanics. In particular, velocity. As money velocity - in other words, currency flux - decreases, the effect upon other segments of the financial system are readily apparent. Liquidity disappears as banks and lenders hoard cash, increasing the chances of "stagflation" -which is currently what they are trying, in order to avoid hyperinflation. The velocity change, in mechanics would theoretically be governed by $F=ma$, $P=mv$ and $KE=\frac{1}{2}mv^2$, (III) meaning that the dæther - if extant - would be capable of providing a force, carrying momentum (and angular momentum), and having a certain amount of energy.

Again, considering money velocity, this would imply that stagnant money hoarded in an account loses more than the liquidity in the economy (system), but that it becomes energetically weak, retaining only what is left from the vibration ($E=hv+mc^2$) and whatever momentum could be had, or more likely *potential energy*. Money is a great MIMS in that it stores potential energy better than most mediums. When treasure is found, or lost money, it liberates tons of spiritual energy in people, usually in the form of excitement and spending. But without that momentum, perhaps the dæther, again if existing and tangibly real, would stipulate that the money can become *inert*. Isn't that exactly what happens with ancient currencies? Lost tokens to laundromats might equal millions of \$\$ in potential value, if amassed, but in reality these tokens are valueless (save perhaps their tin/copper value). (IV) Perhaps the physics or principles of market economics are governed by dæther physics, in particular the interacting junction of the N and P powers.

Proposal

I therefore propose that data scientists, engineers, computer engineers, programmers, mathematicians, etc. work on complex dæther modeling, using hydrodynamics and potentially from there plasma physical “high energy” dynamics to apply to complex and nonlinear systems, looking for evidence of the dætheric model.

Such a complex undertaking requires a special set of skills, and potentially an entire team. But I feel that, like funding the Changes or Shi, it may prove to be worthwhile and lucrative financially to be able to model the numbers, data, information, etc. in non linear means, leaving behind limited Euclidean visualization of the *Numbers* themselves.

(V) If the dæther is modeled as a gas, then various related gas and fluid dynamic laws become important. Consider Bernoulli’s principle. Perhaps the motion of the money would decrease its internal pressure (thus lowering its internal impedance, or increasing its conductance, as it is a currency) and make “greasy palms beget greasy palms.” Perhaps the flow of the financial dæther, representing the total informational energy of the money, will be affected by this principle. So moving money, in this case, would encourage the influx of attendant interested parties, or cause destructive forces (like a tornado or vortex, as it were) to apply pressure upon adjacent “structures” or forms (like businesses, executives themselves, bank ledgers, etc.). It may also prove true that there is the possibility of creating “lift” through data “thrust” and the guiding formation of curved (curled) formations, like certain forms of contracts which are bent, information wise. Having a bent, so to speak, might be a means by which people apply unseen pressures subconsciously to other strictures in their personal reality.

All of this is highly speculative. It became more so in adding the non-mechanical principles of PEM¹⁸, particularly plasma dynamics, to the dæther so as to understand nonlinear dynamics sans equations (or instead of specialized fractal equations, using Newtonian Summations of otherwise linear modeling of gaseous plasmas and fluids, etc.) I don’t propose that this is a real aspect of Nature. Only that it be tested. In other words, this entire section is a hypothesis, and I am not going to be beholden to its failure, but I will take credit for any success. Can I entangle this paper’s data, then in such a way to mimsically support the proposal and move the “dæthere” towards success?

And what, if any direct or indirect, influence shall this discussion have of the previously proposed MIMS 2.101: Dual Layer Economics? If the dæther can be modeled, electrified, etc. (VI) perhaps very reliable simplex models of RLC/analog circuits can be “digitized” and all sorts of various entities which would participate in the DLE be simulated **before launch** of potentially world-altering and dangerous economic changes.

Sincerely,
Sf. R. Careaga

¹⁸ I’d like to acknowledge the potential influence of R. Ashcroft, author of “The Nature of Things” (unpublished) and our discussions as to whether or not there are unique forms of charge. While not exactly the same topic, it is potentially a cross discussion and I’d be remiss not to give him some acknowledgement. Similarly A. Hardin and I have had discussions like this since before I was in contact with R. Ashcroft